

Socrates is Not a Teacher *But Can We Learn from Him?*¹

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Whether it be Socratic Circles, the Socratic Method, or Socratic Seminars, educators using “Socratic” teaching strategies and methods hold the view and accept the conclusion that Socrates employs a reproducible “method” that can be explicated, packaged, marketed and used in the classroom to produce sustainable and reliable results. Freydberg (2007), highly critical of such efforts to reduce Socrates’ philosophy to a method, contends that the Socratic Seminar or Method in education has become a “cliché that refers to hard-hitting question-and-answer exchange quite apart from the concerns with truth and justice that animated Socrates,” and that the method is often flagrantly misused in ways that “Socrates would have found appalling—in training lawyers for instance” (p. 111)—and, we add, within the classroom as an educational method that can be transposed and applied with consistent positive results. For example, Wilberding (2015), within his scripted Socratic curriculum, organizes learning objectives around what he classifies as the *Ten Commandments of Socratic Questions*—systematized Socratic principles for structuring lessons within the curriculum. Undeniably, we can derive beneficial insights from Wilberding’s analysis of Socrates as a teacher; however, our claim is that it is problematic to attach an indelible method of teaching students to Socrates, who would have denied possessing or employing such a method. This is because it is questionable whether or not Socrates *had* a method, and further, whether or not we can even legitimately classify Socrates as a “teacher.” Socrates’ unique pursuit of knowledge differs radically from our pursuits in the contemporary, standardized world of education, which, in the extreme, tends to emphasize skills and determine achievements in learning in ways that are, proximally and for the most part, reducible in a multiplicity of ways to rote assimilation of numerical statistics, results that are quantitative in nature. We are primarily concerned with the analysis of the so-called “Socratic Method” (dialectic) as related to knowledge construction and Socratic ignorance, in defense of the claim that *Socrates is not a teacher*, at least not in the sense of the traditional educator. We conclude by briefly considering the potential benefits that thinkers, educators, and students might draw from our reading, without attempting to establish definitive tenets or principles defining a so-called “Socratic education” in the classroom.

Socrates’ manner of practicing philosophy as we describe it is often referred to as a “method” of inquiry called “*elenchus*,” which is commonly linked with a mode of questioning that seeks to disprove or refute the other’s position. Let us briefly explore the use of “method” and “*elenchus*” when accurately attempting to understand Socrates’ philosophy. Freydberg (2007) points out, “Socrates uses the word *μεθοδος* on very few occasions and never, or perhaps only obliquely, in

¹ I thank the insightful reviewers from the journal for offering suggestions that improved this paper.

reference to his own practice,” and Freydborg continues, observing, “Ἐλεγχος is never called a μεθοδος” (p. 111).¹ It is also the case that “*elenchus*” does not appear with any consistency in the dialogues in a way that would allow us to state with certainty that Socrates’ practice of philosophy should be labeled as such. Tarrant (2009) stresses that we should limit the use of *elenchus* when referring to Socrates’ practice of inquiry to only those instances when he is seeking to refute an interlocutor, while we should refer to what Socrates does most of the time as simply “*exetasis*.” For example, when Socrates is describing to the jury what he does on a daily basis in Athens, setting himself apart from the sophistic teachers of virtue, he says, “I question and examine [ἐξετάσω] and cross-examine [ἐλεξω]” (*Ap.* 29e) the people encountered in the quest to understand virtue, and again at 38a, Socrates states, “I say that to talk every day about virtue” is the greatest thing, and this is why “you hear me talking and examining [ἐξεταζοντος] myself and others.” Indeed, this practice of “examination” is famously, for Socrates, the only antidote for the deadly poison of the “unexamined life”; however, he neither endorses nor adheres to a single, overarching technical or systematic “method.” Our reading is focused on Socrates’ examining himself and others by means of a rigorous practice of testing and scrutinizing opinions and knowledge about virtue through questioning and cross-examination, with the goal or aim stated simply as follows: Socratic philosophy works to arrive, through critical, rational argumentation and consensus, at a deeper understanding of what the virtues are and how they should be best organized within an ethical and excellent life.²

Based on this understanding, we employ the term “dialectic” only throughout when describing Socrates’ philosophical practice. Dialectic, which is set apart from both the didactic method and the instances where Socrates employs *elenchus* refutation, generates both *negative* and *positive* results, indicating that through examining and questioning, Socrates is testing opinions and beliefs about virtue, with an eye to refuting and rejecting arguments put forth in defense of these views that are contradictory, inconsistent, or otherwise problematic, seeking, as the harbinger of enlightenment, to purge “others of their pretense of wisdom” (Brickhouse and Smith, 1984, p. 29).

¹ Two examples of the use of “elenchus” in the Dialogues appear. At Meno 75d, Socrates states: “Your business is to examine and refute it (σὸν ἔργον λαμβάνειν λόγον καὶ ἐλεγεῖν).” In the Apology, when Socrates considers the process of examining men’s lives, he employs the phrase, “ἐλεγχὸν τοῦ βίου” (*Ap.* 39c).

² Referring to Plato, the source, as it were, dialectic is a form of inquiry characterized by the repeated process consisting of the movement between posing a question, receiving a response, and then questioning and testing the rational legitimacy of that response in the service of the continued progress of the investigation or examination. Plato informs us that when practicing dialectic, when *speaking* about what is just and unjust, we work through “names, definitions, and visual and other perceptions,” and when these are “rubbed against each other and tested,” through the process of asking and answering questions, “in good will and without enmity,” it is then, “when reason and knowledge are at the very extremity of human effort, [that] they illuminate the nature of any object” (*Ep.* 344b). In joint pursuit of the understanding (*phronesis*) of the virtues, revelation (*aletheia*) occurs only after “long-continued intercourse”; then, “suddenly, like a light flashing forth when [the] fire [of truth] is kindled, it is born in the soul and straightaway nourishes itself” (*Ep.* 341d).

Socrates works not only to “test and refine definitions of virtues,” but also to “deliberate about right actions, and when the nature of right and wrong action is clear enough,” when a deeper understanding of the virtues is brought to light, Socrates exhorts “others to pursue what is right and shun what is wrong” (p. 29). Importantly for our purposes, Socrates’ dialectic is not restricted to testing others, for as our quotation from the *Apology* demonstrates, Socrates is also intensely concerned with self-examination in the process, and we have more to say about this below in terms of *synerchomai*—which for us means *to go together in learning*. Let us conclude this discussion by turning briefly to the *Charmides*, where Socrates punctuates this point, while intimating the *negative* and *positive* elements of dialectic. Here we encounter Socrates’ concern for both his own soul and the souls of the others engaged in dialectic:

[H]ow could you possibly think that even if I were to refute everything you say, I would be doing it for any other reasons than the one I would give for a thorough investigation of my own statements—the fear of unconsciously thinking I know something when I do not. And this is what I claim to be doing now, examining the argument for my own sake primarily, but perhaps also for the sake of my friends. (*Charm.* 166c-d)

Nehamas (1999) emphatically stresses that Socrates is “not a teacher of *arête*,” but as educators know well, it is undeniably the case that Socrates is often “*perceived* as a teacher,” and beyond, held up as a paragon of pedagogy to be emulated and imitated (p. 62). At his trial, Socrates is accused of “wrongdoing because he corrupts the youth and does not believe in the gods the state believes in” (*Ap.* 24c). Beyond these charges, he is accused, in the manner of Anaxagoras and other Greek physical scientists, of “investigating the things beneath the earth and in the heavens,” and also charged, in the manner of the sophists, with “making the weaker argument stronger.” Importantly, Socrates is, according to his accusers, “teaching [*διδασκων*/*didaskon*] these things to others” (*Ap.* 19b-c). In his defense (*apologia*), Socrates distances himself from both the natural philosophers and the sophists, such as Gorgias of Leontini, Prodicus of Ceos, and Hippias of Elis, who all charge fees for their services and usually teach through speeches or didactic methods that communicate or transfer knowledge to their pupils. In light of these remarks, returning to Nehamas, although his accusers, and even his friends, consider Socrates a teacher, this offers no valid reason or sufficient evidence for us “to refuse to take his own disavowal of that role at face value” (p. 71). The Greek “*διδασκαλος*” (*didaskalos*) defines a “teacher or master” of one or another subject, such as rhetoric, medicine, craft making, or even poetry (*Lexicon* 2015, p. 169). With the understanding of the *didaskalos* related to the type of instruction in virtue (*arête*) offered by the sophists, it is against the charges of Meletus that Socrates emphatically denies that he is a teacher, specifically of the virtues, claiming that he “was never anyone’s teacher” (*Ap.* 33a).

Scott (2000) provides us with four distinct characteristics that define the *didaskalos*: (1) the *didaskalos* is an authority; he possesses the knowledge he imparts through transmission to students who do not know; (2) the *didaskalos* demands payment for his teaching; (3) the *didaskalos* teaches only upon receipt of payment; indeed, without payment there is no instruction; and (4) the *didaskalos* (the knower) instructs through expository speeches employing didactic methods designed to communicate or transfer knowledge to the paying client, the non-knower or learner. We add to this list, (5) the *didaskalos* has a responsibility toward a student based on the service that is to be rendered, i.e., since the sophist takes payment for imparting knowledge to the pupil, a

sense of responsibility for the learning must obtain; in short, a sophist is liable for the end product of his labors. This is precisely what Plato's Socrates denies; "I cannot justly be held responsible for the good or bad conduct of these people, as I never promised to *teach* [*didasko*] them anything and have not done so" (*Ap.* 33a-b), and in addition, he adds, "If you have heard from anyone that I undertake to teach people and charge a fee for it, that is not true either" (*Ap.* 19d-e).¹ Recall the disastrous results that ensued when the young men imitated Socrates, contributing to the formulation of the charges against him. When the youth attempted to copy and employ Socrates' supposed "method," performing *elenchus* refutations of prominent Athenian citizens, they encountered many people who thought they had knowledge, but in truth were shown to sorely lack the knowledge they claimed to possess, and as a result, the Athenians who were examined and shamed by the youths became angry with Socrates (*Ap.* 32c-e). It is crucial to note, in relation to our theme, that as opposed to training or teaching (*didasko*) these youths to be upstart "gadflies," it was through chance and neither by Socrates' design nor via the implementation of any formal instructional strategy that these youths were inspired to imitate him. Socrates did not, even in an indirect manner, "teach" the youths anything valuable about his practice of philosophy or the virtues.

From our description of the *didaskalos*, it is possible to infer a view of education associated with this type of teacher, and it is a form of learning, according to King (1976), which works off the "additive," or what we refer to as the "edifice" model of knowledge acquisition through the primary mode of transfer. In the *additive model* new knowledge is piled on previous knowledge in a manner resembling the accumulation of a growing store of knowledge, and as King importantly stresses, in this mode of learning, the knower as receiver is passive. Educators are probably most familiar with this model in terms of the "factory model" of learning or, in the Marxist-existential inspired critical theory-pedagogy of Freire (2000), the "banking concept of education" (p. 72). If we relate it to Socrates' understanding of education, it would be closely akin to what we term a *productionist* model of learning, and this is consistent with the *technē/epistēmē-poiesis-ergon* model of craft making, which is employed when a master, one who is an authority or expert, passes along his expertise to the apprentice, one who lacks the knowledge of the expert. Brickhouse and Smith (1984) observe that Plato often uses *technē* and *epistēmē* interchangeably when referring to the knowledge of both the craftsman and the sophists, and in the dialogues, "Socrates' claim to lack *ἐπιστήμη* (knowledge)," in relation to understanding the virtues, "is contrasted directly with the craftsmen's having it" (p. 33). The type of knowledge linked with the *productionist* model introduced is precise and explanatory, it affords the possessor a reasonable if

¹ We stated that Socrates refused responsibility for the behavior of those who participated in philosophical discussions. In line with our reading regarding the results or outcomes of these discussions, we consider the following: *If indeed Socrates was a teacher*, and his so-called instruction had a positive, educative influence on the ethical disposition of the participants, why did many of the interlocutors with whom he discoursed become rouges, ne'er-do-wells, and even violent tyrants? For example, in the case of Alcibiades, betrayer of both Athens and Sparta, Socrates could not muster the power to "teach" him anything that might have *turned his soul around* in an ethical manner, and indeed Alcibiades admits this in the *Symposium*. For a discussion of the so-called "Failure of Alcibiades' Education," see Magrini, J. M. (2021). *Politics of the Soul in the Alcibiades*. New York: Peter Lang.

not a confident sense of *predictability*, and as Kirkland (2010) contends, “one who possesses it knows not only what is the case but why this must be so, making it therefore teachable” (p. 80). This is why it is transferable from master to apprentice, as in the case of architects, engineers and, as is often mentioned by Socrates, physicians.

Socrates distrusts this “banking model” of education as a mode of transfer-learning, specifically as it relates to *normative* issues of value and human excellence, for according to Socrates, this is not the manner in which anyone learns to be virtuous; we will have more to say regarding Socratic philosophy and *normativity* as we proceed. The critique of transfer-learning is made explicit in the dialogues, e.g., in the *Symposium*; Agathon hopes to “absorb” knowledge from Socrates as it is passed through didactic transfer, to which Socrates slyly responds, “Wouldn’t it be marvelous, Agathon, if ideas were the kind of things which could be imparted simply by contact, and those of us who had few could absorb them from those who had a lot—in the same way that liquid can flow from a full container to an empty one if you put a piece of string between them?” (*Smp.* 175d). The exchange indicates that Agathon believes knowledge can be divined, possessed, and then passed along with certainty to others lacking in knowledge. For the type of education and learning Agathon stresses is, according to Socrates, sophistic and technical in nature, indicating that truth can be secured and possessed in a form that resists disambiguation when transferred from one person to another. Indeed, it is in the *Protagoras* that the Socratic question of whether virtue is teachable or transferable emerges in its most well-known and detailed form. The pressing concern, which ultimately separates the philosopher (the seeker and lover of virtue) from the sophist (the one who claims to have virtue) runs thusly: If virtue “turns out to be entirely knowledge [*επισημη*],” it would therefore be teachable; however, “if virtue [*αρετη*] were anything else than knowledge [*επισημη*] ... obviously it would not be teachable” (*Prot.* 361a-b). Thus, we conclude, along with Kirkland (2010), if virtue could be reduced to *episteme*, it would provide Socrates “the propositional definitions he demands,” along with the subsequent ability to defend those definitions “from *elenctic* refutation” (p. 7-8). Such a view, as we contend throughout, runs counter to Socrates’ conception of the understanding, or *phronesis*, of the virtues that dialectic makes possible.¹

¹ In the Dialogues, *techne* and *episteme* are separated off from opinions and belief and also the knowledge or understanding Socrates seeks of the virtues, which is often rendered as *sophia*, but also, more consistently, as *phronesis* or a derivative thereof. In *Definitions*, a late work probably compiled by students of Plato’s *Academy*, we read, “*Phronesis*—practical wisdom ... productive of human happiness” (*Def.* 411d). Importantly, to the issue of *episteme*, although the *Lexicon* (2015) links it to the Greek understanding of “*scientific knowledge*,” it also informs us that it can simply indicate “*understanding, skill, and wisdom*” (p. 261). Even in the *Republic* Plato does not suggest that *episteme* gives the philosopher rulers sure and certain knowledge of the so-called “*Forms*,” for the type of knowing that reveals “first principles” by means of intellectual intuition is “*noesis*,” a form of knowledge or insight that for Socrates, in his idealized vision of the perfected *city of words*, demonstrates categorical certainty. In a way that draws on the certainty of *axiomatic* truth in mathematics, Plato claims that through dialectic we make our way to a “first principle that is *not* a hypothesis,” but proceeding from a hypothesis, “using forms themselves and making the investigation through them” (*Rep.* 510b). As one reviewer of this paper astutely points out, which it is essential to mention within the context of our discussion about knowledge forms, scholars writing on Plato and Socrates must be attentive to the fact that when equating certainty with

Admittedly, in the *Meno* it is possible to state that Socrates does indeed share some similarities with the description of the *didaskalos* from above, despite adopting a dialectical mode of projective questioning, especially when Socrates educates Meno's slave boy in geometry. In this instance Socrates appears to instantiate the *Socrates-as-teacher* model embraced and imitated by those practicing Socratic Seminar, the so-called educator as *guide-on-the-side*. We note that the *Meno* is one of several dialogues, along with the *Gorgias* and *Lysis*, from which the *Socrates-as-teacher* model is drawn, and indeed, the view of *Socrates-as-teacher* is most often justified through a standard interpretation of the *Meno*. In this dialogue Socrates leads Meno's young slave to the knowledge of Euclidean geometry through a series of questions and statements designed specifically to enlighten and awaken the boy to the knowledge that is supposedly already present within his soul.¹ However, when examining the dialogue we note that there are two forms of dialectic and types of educating transpiring, one a mode of *teaching* and the other the practice of what King (1976) calls *non-teaching*, or what we identify, along with Socrates, as a dialectical process of co-learning or *seeking together*. Thus we encounter (1) a “positive” or “constructive”

episteme as a knowledge form, they run the danger of conflating “scientific” knowledge with propositional certitude. Science, as now practiced, as it is divorced from what might be labeled “Newtonian predictive certainty,” more resembles the type of inquiry embraced and practiced by Socrates, which, as we have argued, is continually in the process of revising its conclusions and renewing its inquiries. On this foregoing point, Gonzalez (1998) shares a similar view about the misconception of method in Plato, but Gonzalez's claim relates to the reviewer's comments on science and its method: Gonzalez argues that it is a misinterpretation of Plato to fall victim to the assumption that “philosophical *method* is subordinate to, and terminates in, some final result” (p. 9). For this wrongly gives the impression that apart from “the method of inquiry, a system exists which is thought to be the end (in both senses of the word) of the method,” and this leads to the inevitable destruction of the process of inquiry (p. 9). For in this view—which Gonzalez links to “doctrinal” or “orthodox” readings of Plato—the “process of questioning and investigating has a terminus that ultimately renders this process no longer necessary” (p. 9). This view of inquiry stands at odds with both our reading of Plato's Socrates and the understanding of how the contemporary scientific method operates as indicated by the reviewer.

¹ Prior to the geometry lesson, Socrates discusses the immortal soul and suggests that all learning is recollection (*αναμνησις/anamnesis*), intimating the remembrance of our past life when dwelling with the *Forms*, and this in Sahakian and Sahakian (1977) is identified, and I would argue incorrectly, as the *Doctrine of the Immortal Soul* and the *Doctrine of Anamnesis* in Platonic philosophy. However, we note that Socrates cuts this line of discussion short, abruptly insisting that this “captious argument” should be avoided (*Men.* 81c). Instead, what he describes resembles inference in learning, i.e., by recalling one thing, we can then work from there to recall or learn another in relation to the first (*Men.* 81d). It is unnecessary to attach mysterious, religious, or transcendent meanings to the term “*anamnesis*,” for the way Socrates carries out the Geometry lesson resembles what the *Lexicon* (2015) states is “*calling [something] to mind*” within a process where new insight dawns based on or inspired by what one already knows or has learned. To reiterate, *anamnesis* might be an instance of logical inference (p. 52). Although this Socratic lesson is undeniably impressive and inspirational, there is nothing other-worldly, religious, or mysterious about it.

dialectic concerned with mathematical or *axiomatic* truth that is set or nested within (2) the larger and overarching context of dialectical examination that is both “negative” and “positive” in its unfolding, ending in *aporia* as is consistent with Socratic discourse practiced throughout the Platonic dialogues (especially, but certainly not limited to, the early dialogues). This form of dialectic is ultimately focused on ethical (*normative*) issues and questions regarding the nature of virtue and the concern for whether it can be acquired with certainty and subsequently taught or transferred to a pupil without dissembling. Taylor (2001) is one of the only Platonic scholars explicating for analysis the realm of the *normative* in Socratic discourse, this despite Plato’s never naming or making this modern epistemological distinction. Taylor informs us that when referring to the *normative* in Socratic interpretation, we are naming the things in life that are of supreme value (*axios*), which for Socrates is a concern for the ethical, the concern for those things that *should* be pursued and *ought* to be done in relation to and in pursuit of a life of moral excellence.¹

The first dialectic, where Socrates takes the boy through a geometry lesson, might be said to represent educators employing the “Socratic Method,” or *Socrates-as-teacher* model. Although the boy has no prior knowledge of mathematics, through a series of leading questions, and the fact that Plato’s Socrates has knowledge of geometry, the boy is able to solve the problem, i.e., the slave boy is led to the knowledge that Socrates possesses. In the geometry lesson we encounter *aporetic* breakdowns in the process of learning, for when the boy is unable to follow Socrates’ line of questioning, he becomes confused, but importantly, this is not the case with Socrates (*Men.* 84e). Indeed, such occurrences are, for Socrates, valuable moments rife with potential for new insight, and in the geometry lesson, Socrates uses these moments as a valuable teaching tool. Within these moments, which Socrates controls and manipulates, the boy “feels the difficulty he is in, and besides not knowing does not think he knows” (*Men.* 84a), and so with prompting and encouragement (*protreptic*), the boy seeks to “push on in the search gladly, as lacking knowledge” (*Men.* 84b). Although Socrates states that as a result of this “perplexity” (*tes aporias*), the boy will go on to learn with Socrates (“joint-inquiry”), and further, that Socrates will not technically be “teaching” the boy (*Men.* 84d), it is clear that Socrates has the knowledge of mathematics required to complete the lesson and bring the boy to enlightenment. So, as opposed to Socrates’

¹ I thank the reviewer who asked for clarification regarding the “normative” or *normativity* in Socratic philosophy for students reading this essay who might be unfamiliar with the term. There is no Greek word in the Dialogues that Plato incorporates that is the equivalent of the Latin “*norma*,” concerned with patterns, rules, and precepts. In the Greek, the idea of the *normative* is traceable to what Socrates understands as “*nomos*” and “*nomoi*,” expressive of laws, traditions, principles, and rules. Socrates, focused on values and ethics, formulates, communicates, and defends arguments presented in the form of “normative statements” rather than exclusively in the form of propositions. Certainly, Plato does not formulate the issue of the *fact/value* distinction in terms of Hume’s modern understanding, but it is present within the Dialogues; thus, although “unsaid,” it is certainly not “unthought” by Plato, despite its lack of systematic classification. Clearly, as this essay indicates, Socrates is concerned with “norms” of behavior that are regulative of ethical conduct, and concerned with judging and determining, through dialogue, through deliberating well (*boule*) on the good and true about what actions *should* and *ought* to be done and what actions *should* be avoided in service to the ethical life. Indeed, as we learn, this deliberation is actually “*koine boule*” (“common deliberation”) in Socratic philosophy, a deliberating well in the company of and with others.

personally experiencing the confusion of the *aporetic* breakdown in the pursuit of knowledge, coming to the conclusion that *he himself* does not know, as he does in the second dialectic concerned with virtue, Socrates in this case is using the moment of confusion (*aporia*), or *learned ignorance*, to the boy's educational advantage. Socrates, to reiterate, is not the one inferring the knowledge of geometry or learning it; rather, he is imparting it, through a unique pedagogical strategy consisting of questioning, a mode of teaching that although not didactic in nature, still depends on and presupposes that Socrates has the knowledge required to enlighten the boy, the student. Here, we are not diminishing the educative significance of *aporetic* breakdown in the lesson, the difficult moment of acknowledging ignorance, which holds the potential to inspire continued inquiry. We are, however, pointing out that in this instance Socrates is not experiencing *aporia* in a manner that would indicate that he truly does not know the things he investigates, as in the case of the second dialectic in the *Meno*.

The second dialectic deals with the question of whether or not virtue is teachable, and also, perhaps more importantly, with the question of what virtue is, the Socratic question: "What-is-*x*?" (*ti esti?*). In the second form of dialectic, unlike the geometry lesson, the conclusions regarding whether or not virtue can be taught are not only unsatisfactory; they are confused, and as Nehamas (1999) stresses, this is because no agreeable definition is or can be provided in response to the perennial Socratic question, "what *is* virtue?" that would foreclose continued discussion and argumentation. As discussed, the teacher must possess knowledge and know *that* something is the case in order to give a reasoned account of *what* is true and *how* it is true in order to impart it or even lead others to it. In addition, the teacher has mastered the method to be employed in order to secure knowledge, and he must then be able to instruct the pupil in the proper practice of dialectic in order to bring the student to a state of enlightenment. This indicates, and here Nehamas asks us to keep in mind Socrates' unique philosophical project, that it is necessary that Socrates possess, and hence be a master of (*didaskalos*), much like in the geometry lesson, both the "knowledge (*episteme*) of *arête* and the craft (*techne*) of teaching it" (p. 69). This demands that one have or possess knowledge and that one can articulate it through explanation and ultimately pass it along through transfer, or bring it about through the formulation and application of a series of pointed, leading questions, "with reasonable assurance of success" (p. 69). Weiss (2009) also contributes to this line of reasoning when asserting that in order for Socrates to be a master or expert instructor (*didaskalos*) in virtue, he would need to acquire objective knowledge of the virtues, or what Weiss calls *theoretical definitions*. For to have such knowledge, which for Socrates is impossible due to the built-in limitations of all *normative* concerns, would amount to establishing "a *god's* eye perspective [*sub specie aeternitas*]" (p. 157), and to have access to such a perspective would require a person to be either a god or god-like. Not only does Socrates reject god-like knowledge, but he claims that "human wisdom" is essentially pervaded by a lack of complete knowledge—pervasive *dialectic ignorance*—for according to Socrates, when compared to the gods' wisdom, "Human wisdom [*ανθρωπινη σοφια*] is of little or no value" (*Ap.* 23a). As Nehamas (1999) stresses, because the philosophical "domain in which Socrates is concerned is exclusively *ethical*," i.e., *normative*, the type of knowledge required in order to teach the virtues to anyone is the precise form of knowledge that defies sure and certain possession and transmission, and for this reason continually eludes Socrates (p. 69).

Indeed, Socrates' entire philosophical project, as *care for the soul*, is dedicated to pointing out and inspiring in others the necessary recognition of *ignorance*—of not-knowing—regarding the most

important things in life, namely, the philosophical pursuit of the virtues along with the concomitant understanding of their proper role and place in a life of *eudaemonia*. Here, when referring to εὐδαιμονία/*eudaemonia*, we are not suggesting, as does Bobonich (2011), that Socrates practices a system of either *rational eudaimonism* or *psychological eudaimonism*, but rather that Socrates seeks a life directed toward the *idea* and *ideal* of personal (private) and communal (public) perfection that is grounded in and inspired by notions of the good and of ethical excellence. Scott (2000) contends that Socrates assumes “the role as a *paideutes*” (31), and let us note that in the Greek, “*παιδευτής/paideutes*” is not a term that is interchangeable with the teaching or instruction of the *didaskalos*, for *paideutes*, as the *Lexicon* (2015) confirms, references “*an educator*” that assumes the critical role of a “*corrector, chastiser,*” and beyond, one that participates in the process of learning in such an intimate way that the educator’s character, disposition, and state of soul are at stake; education in this view consists of both the receiving and bestowing of an education.¹ In line with this understanding, Socrates is more of a seeker (*zeteos*), or “lover of wisdom,” than one who is in the possession of truth or knowledge of the virtues (e.g., *Meno* 80c; *Tht.* 155d; *Phds.* 278d; *Gor.* 506a; *Al. I* 124a-c), who often assumes the role of co-participant or co-learner in the dialectical context of the investigation. The limited nature of Socrates’ understanding (*phronesis*) of the virtues, a way of knowing that can never be wholly trustworthy or complete, locates him “in-between” the ultimate wisdom of the gods and the bare, unacknowledged ignorance of those who do not practice philosophy (*Sym.* 202a-b). If there is a superiority to Socrates’ knowledge, if indeed Socrates can be called “wise” (*Ap.* 21d), and we must note that what he knows and the degree to which he knows it fails to qualify him as a teacher (*didaskalos*), it is to be found in his *superior* understanding of what the philosophical life encompasses and entails, which includes, as we have already stated, being attuned to the limited nature of all human wisdom.

In addition to misrepresenting the form of knowledge associated with the Socratic dialectic, the *Socrates-as-teacher* model also appears to discount the legitimacy of Socrates’ claims to ignorance regarding the wisdom of the virtues, interpreting him as *ironically* masquerading as a co-participant in dialectic, when in reality Socrates is in possession of the knowledge, holding the answers up his sleeve, as it were. This view incorrectly locates Socrates at a radical hierarchical (epistemological) distance from the interlocutor, as one who is far superior in his absolute possession of knowledge. It also, as stated above, wrongly presupposes that Socrates as educator already knows where he wants to lead the student and does so by framing a series of pointed questions, which if answered correctly, will lead the student down the path toward what appears to be authentic self-discovery. Such a position, argues Nehamas (1999), wrongly assumes that irony is “saying one thing and meaning the opposite,” for when interpreting Socrates *as* ironist, as someone in actual possession of the truth he is denying, the “holding back is part of the trope” (p. 71). This view is similar to Vlastos’ (1991) reading, wherein he argues that although Socrates is not a teacher who adopts a method of rote transfer, he is indeed a teacher in another and more

¹ Based on our reading, in conjunction with Davey’s (2006) understanding and analysis of philosophical hermeneutics, it is possible to establish an intimate connection between Socratic *paideusis* and *Bildung* as a form of education highlighted by personal involvement, the formation of the character, and the transformation of the intellect and soul, as this might be related to the moderate hermeneutics of Gadamer, who has given us many detailed hermeneutic studies of Plato’s dialogues.

important sense, one who engages potential “learners in elenctic argument to make them aware of their own ignorance and enable them to discover for themselves the truth the teacher had held back,” and so, as Vlastos concludes, “Socrates would want to say that he is a teacher, the only true teacher” (p. 32). This conclusion apparently ignores critical evidence from the dialogues regarding Socrates’ emphatic disavowal of knowledge, which indicates, as we have argued, that Socrates truly does not *hold back* any knowledge of virtue in dialectic, and rather, through his recognition of ignorance, seeks to further pursue it.

As opposed to reducing Socrates’ claims of ignorance to examples of Socratic irony or the Platonic incorporation of a literary trope, it is on this point, as Nehamas (1999) emphasizes, that “we should take Socrates very seriously, if rather literally, when he insists that he does not teach anyone anything” (p. 19). The failure to acknowledge and take seriously the literal nature of Socrates’ claims to ignorance “robs him of much of his strangeness”; conversely, taking seriously Socrates’ claims to *not knowing* actually “supplies him, paradoxically, with a much more profound ironical mask” (p. 71). Nehamas gives us a nuanced and complex treatment of Socratic irony in which it represents an instance where “not-knowing” actually grounds the instantiation of Socrates’ philosophical project, which is inseparable from attempting to live an ethical life. In other words, despite Socrates’ disavowing the possession of the form of ethical knowledge that would be required to be a teacher, Socrates is nevertheless and for that reason someone whose practice of philosophy embodies the paradigmatic “ethical life,” even though he is unable to pass the “truth” of the virtues along to those with whom he engages in dialogue. This is because he could not categorize it, systematize it, or formalize it in such a way as is required for educational transmission, but despite this, he realizes that the pursuit of this understanding (*phronesis*) of the virtues, even though the full-disclosure of their “truth” forever resides beyond the human’s full grasp, calls for and even demands the unwavering devotion to a philosophical life-style, and this for Socrates is the most ethical way in which to live.

Despite perceptions to the contrary, Socrates does not view himself as a teacher of virtue, and indeed, as Nehamas (1999) observes, Socrates’ “*moral stature* derives directly from his *refusal to accept that role*” (p. 62), based on his *ignorance* of the sure and certain meaning of the virtues. Jaspers (1962), in his *existential-phenomenological* reading of Plato’s dialogues and philosophy, refers to the *fundamental sense of irony* in Socrates as that “which strives to give an intimation of the hidden truth” (p. 27).¹ In line with Nehamas’ reading, Jaspers also interprets Socratic irony in terms of an expression of Socrates’ authentic claims to *not having knowledge*, for irony, claims Jaspers, actually “provokes the knowledge of non-knowledge” (p. 27), e.g., in the crucial function of “confusion” or *aporia* in Socratic dialectic, which emerges as both the *positive* philosophical content and the function of dialectic. According to Jaspers, Socratic irony unmasks through sheltering and concealing “the candid awareness of what one does not know,” and by means of this “one will arrive not at nothingness but at the knowledge that is crucial for life” (p. 7). Even though dialectic as practiced by Socrates, through reasoned and rigorous exchange, reaches a point where there is consensus regarding the “temporary” truth of the issue under investigation, Socrates urges his interlocutors to continue working toward deeper modes of understanding by continually

¹ For a unique analysis of Plato as a proto-phenomenological philosopher in relation to Jasper’s *existenz* philosophy, see Magrini, J. M. (2017). Interpreting Karl Jasper’s “Phenomenological” Plato. *Existenz* 2, 34-48. Retrieved from <http://www.Existenz.us.Vol.12-Magrini.html>.

questioning their findings. Listening to Socrates' words, we ask the reader to recall our earlier description of dialectic:

[A]ll of us ought to be contentiously eager to know what's true and what's false about the things we're talking about.... I'll go through the discussion, then, and say how I think it is, and if any of you thinks that what I agree to with myself isn't so, you must object and refute me. For the things I say I certainly don't say with any knowledge at all; no, I'm searching together with you so that if my opponent clearly has a point, I'll be the first to concede it (*Gorg.* 506a).

Since the validity of the claims regarding the virtues that are brought to stand momentarily through the *logos* in dialogic-consensus refuse, in Socrates' words, to be "held down and bound by arguments of iron and adamant" (*Gor.* 508a), it is impossible for Socrates to possess the knowledge required to assume the role of *didaskalos*, and so he cannot be a teacher in this sense, for he admits that he both lacks the knowledge in question and that he is a legitimate and dedicated "co-participant" (*co-learner*) in dialectic. In relation to what we have said about that manner in which *normative* statements function, manifesting the difference between *episteme* and *phronesis*, contrasting, as Mittelstrass (1988) points out, with "the systematic constraints of textbooks and treatises" (p. 140), the understanding (*phronesis*) of the virtues is fluid and elusive in nature and holds only the precarious potential to inspire and facilitate ethically informed "attitudes," transforming the disposition (*hexis*) and soul (*psyche*) by informing and shaping the *philosophical orientation* of those participating in dialectic. In essence, it is the lack of possession of *episteme*, or some other "objective" form of knowledge, as Nehamas (1999) emphasizes, which prevents Plato's Socrates "from being a teacher of the good life" (p. 67). This represents the crucial issue that Socrates continues to struggle with throughout the dialogues, namely, as we have shown, the difference between "dialectic and craft," which is to say the difference between "pure persuasion by means of argument" and an "authority that can justify itself by its tried-and-true accomplishments" (p. 69). The latter of these two views relates to our earlier discussion of the *factory model* of learning in standardized education, and this represents, to reiterate, a *productionist* model of learning consistent with the *techne/episteme-poesis-ergon* model of craft-making, of which Socrates is critical when relating it to understanding the virtues.

Bringing this analysis to a conclusion, let us now consider the exchange following Meno's frustration during the dialogue's *aporetic* breakdown where we encounter an authentic instance of Socratic ignorance in the dialogue, which might be understood as synonymous with "learning" in Socratic terms. Recall that when previously discussing *aporia* in the geometry lesson, it was only the boy who truly experienced the confusion and frustration of "not-knowing." Yet here, as we have pointed out, in the ongoing discussion concerned with virtue, it is Socrates who is also befuddled and confused, because he too experiences and so participates in the *aporetic* breakdown in questioning. For when Meno becomes exhausted with Socrates' questioning, he claims that Socrates, in a shrewd and beguiling manner, possesses the power of a "broad-torpedo fish" because Socrates stings and numbs interlocutors as part of his unique method of dialectical teaching. This analogy gives the surface impression that Socrates is in possession of knowledge and that his teaching strategy is designed to confuse or confound the pupil before finally revealing the knowledge that was in his possession all along, as in the aforementioned geometry lesson. Indeed, this is not the case, and Socrates assures Meno of this when stating that he does not possess sure

and certain knowledge of virtue, but is ignorant of its nature, and further, that the pursuit of such knowledge must be carried out in terms of a joint *zetetic*-educative venture, i.e., “to examine and seek together” (*skepsasthai kai suzetetesai*) within the context of co-participatory learning. Unlike with the “additive” model introduced earlier, King (1976) claims that this type of “joint-learning” resembles an “integrative” model of education as “non-teaching,” which is expressive of an active interpretive process through which understanding is revealed and reworked, reassessed, reconfigured, and rearranged. In addition, it is possible to state that in this educational model both the form and content of the learning are at issue as related directly to the enlightenment and transformation of the dispositions and souls of those participating in the process of dialectic. Socrates, setting irony aside, assures Meno that he does not resemble the stinging fish, because the fish does not wound or numb itself when stinging and numbing its prey. For Socrates declares that when he “perplexes” others, he is just as perplexed as they are: “It is from being in more doubt than anyone else,” observes Socrates, “that I cause doubt in others” (*Men.* 80d). Socrates continues, asserting, “I do not know what virtue is,” but nevertheless, “I want to examine and seek together [*σκεψασθαι και συζητησαι*] with you what it may be” (*Men.* 80d).

Scott (2000) contributes to our reading when observing what might be termed, with caution, the “Socratic education process,” which is inseparable from the practice of Socratic dialectic, and is “guided by an erotic striving in which both teacher and student become co-seekers (*sunerastes*) after truths which are sure to be difficult to express and which turn out to be harder still to discover” (p. 47). Although we are skeptical of Scott’s use of “teacher and student,” which connotes a traditional, asymmetrical pairing in education, we agree with his interpretation of the so-called “educational context” comprised of co-participants or *co-learners* united in the quest—“*συνερχομαι/synorchomai*,” “to go along with or together”—to search out together trust-worthy responses to the “what is *x*?” question. As related to the *Gorgias*, *Meno*, and *Charmides*, in the *Alcibiades I*,¹ we also encounter notions of co-learning, for although Socrates clearly has a greater understanding of what is entailed when caring for the soul than does Alcibiades, there is, nevertheless, a clear indication that Socrates is legitimately embracing and acknowledging the limits of his own knowledge, professing the acceptance of his ignorance. Socrates assures Alcibiades that they are both “in need of education” and that Socrates will participate as a “co-learner” in the process of interrogating “justice” (*dikaio-sune*) in the service of “self-cultivation” while dedicated to deepening his own self-knowledge in dialogue with Alcibiades. Far from giving Alcibiades the impression that he’s a teacher of virtue, Socrates suggests that they should “take council together” (*koine boule*) in dialectic. When young Alcibiades asks Socrates to show him, or teach him, the art of self-cultivation, which is the process of becoming educated in the virtues, Socrates suggests the following: “Let us discuss together how *we can become* as good as possible. You know, what I’ve said about *the need for education applies to me as well as you* (*Alc. I* 124b-c; my emphasis). Let us note, as Denyer (2001) observes, that despite Socrates’ perpetual claims to ignorance of the virtues, we must acknowledge that he is morally superior to all of his

¹ It is generally agreed upon among Platonic scholars that Plato is not the author of this dialogue, which is often classified amongst the *Apocrypha*. Taylor (2001) disputes its authorship but does have praise for it, stating that it is worth reading and analyzing: “This [the *Alcibiades I*] is in compass and worth the most important member of the group [*Apocrypha*], as it contains an excellent general summary of the Socratic-Platonic doctrines of the scale of good and the ‘tendance’ of the soul” (p. 522).

interlocutors based on what he has learned in his diligent and relentless philosophical pursuit of understanding the virtues. However, in line with our argument, Socrates undoubtedly benefits from the discussions within which he participates, for through the process he learns more about himself and those with whom he is engaged in discourse. Despite the sure and certain knowledge of the virtue in question evading Socrates' firm grasp, he undoubtedly benefits through his participation with Alcibiades as *co-learner* in the examination.

We began with a brief discussion about Socratic Method in education, and highlighted the fact that it is questionable and even problematic to claim to “teach like Socrates.” Indeed, we went so far as to suggest that Socrates really doesn't have a method, if by method we mean a transferable schema for learning, which can be formalized and applied with predictable results. Our reading exposed the chasm dividing educators embracing the Socratic Method in classroom instruction and Socrates as he appears in Plato's dialogues, where he practices the non-systematic, open-ended form of dialectical examination. The question remains: If Socrates is not a teacher in the traditional sense, if he disavows claims to the type of knowledge required to be a teacher in the first instance, are there lessons we can learn or at least draw from his unique practice of philosophy as presented? We answer in the affirmative. For example, as an instructor of philosophy and ethics, it is often the case that I look to Socrates for inspiration, drawing out new ways to conceive myself in relation to my students, new ways to imagine education as something other than a means of transmitting knowledge, as a *product* of learning, to students who are being prepared for their marketable vocational futures. As we have shown, Socrates is far more concerned with turning our attention, as both educators and students, to the supreme value to be found in the pursuit of an ethical education, or in less formal terms, the quest to improve, to whatever degree possible, our attitudes toward, and the values we hold about, ourselves, others, and the world. Space does not allow us to compile a lengthy list of so-called “benefits” that might be derived from Socratic philosophy; indeed, many books have been written on this topic. However, although not attempting to systematize his process and offer for the reader indelible principles or even loose tenets of a Socratic education, there are three crucial aspects of Socratic *philosophia* that are worth mentioning in relation to our study—all of which, we might say, serve as preconditions for philosophizing and the enactment of authentic learning.

First, Socrates' philosophy, which is inseparable from the practice of dialectic, demands the acknowledgement and acceptance of the limited nature of human knowledge. For as against dogmatism, the enemy of Socratic inquiry, admitting one's lack of or privation of knowledge (ignorance) is essential for beginning and for inspiring and facilitating the continued and renewed pursuit of philosophical enlightenment, despite the limited nature of that enlightenment. This might be called the *philosophical acknowledgement of human finitude*. Second, rather than teaching, Socrates brings our attention to the supreme importance of co-learning, where the quest for knowledge and enlightenment, the pursuit of the reasoned understanding (*phronesis*) of the virtues, is carried out in communal dialogue through a form of examination that is precarious and unpredictable, difficult to manage, and monumentally demanding because of the stakes involved for all participants. For Socrates, what is ultimately at stake is the perfection of the soul or enlightened transformation of the ethical dispositions of all those involved. Communal discourse, however, always holds the potential danger to expose the vulnerability of our finite and fragile human natures, and so an intimate form of trust is required, because in the process of co-learning, our most cherished, long-held beliefs are rigorously challenged, put into question in such a way

that it calls for their reassessment, and in some instances, demands their rejection. The quest for self-improvement through dialectic is always already inextricably bound up with the potential improvement of others, and out of this type of co-learning a sense of communal or ecumenical possibilities also arises, indicating that in the process of revealing and appropriating my possibilities in relation to others, there is a collective transformation in learning also occurring. This we might say is the enlightening *philosophical process of becoming other in the face of the other*. Third, as opposed to answers or definitive solutions to the weighty ethical problems we face, Socrates shows us that we are more often than not confronted with the task of formulating appropriate questions about the things we deem the most valuable and meaningful. The pursuit of virtue calls for us to formulate original questions about the ethical life, queries about how to live in an excellent manner, questions that shape, guide, and direct the unfolding of our investigations. However, as we have shown, these inquiries and problems defy categorical answers and solutions, and this pushes us into the presence of all that is and must remain *questionable*, for such things demand further examination and require the formulation of new and different questions. Socrates inspires us to live in a way that instantiates learning as a life-long endeavor, task and vocation, because philosophically questioning the ethical life, although remaining an incomplete task, is for Socrates the most worthwhile and rewarding thing we can do, and this we call the Socratic *devotion to live a question-worthy existence*. Indeed, outside of the single fatality of death, Socrates demonstrates that it is possible and desirable to continue the search for wisdom. However, we must note that Socrates is unwilling to acknowledge or conclude with utter certainty that human learning truly ends with death (*Ap.* 41a-b).

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